

On the Utilization of Graphene Derivatives for Microwave Applications

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Abstract. Thanks to its remarkable properties, graphene has provoked the interest of research community in the last years. Moreover, the simple top-down synthesis of chemically modified graphene materials, such as graphene oxide (GO) or reduced graphene oxide (rGO), opens new possibilities for an easier and more feasible fabrication. However, relatively few applications have been proposed and realistically assessed for microwave devices. Here we provide a brief overview of the main enablers and challenges of the utilization of graphene derivatives for microwave applications.

1 Introduction

Since the discovery of isolated and stable graphene films by Novoselov et. al. in 2004 [1], graphene has gained the interest of the whole research community due to its promising mechanical, thermal and optical properties, which include good electrical conductivity, high optical transmittance, elevated Young's modulus, and thermal conductivity [2], among others. In a first instance, graphene samples were obtained through mechanical exfoliation of highly ordered pyrolytic graphite (HOPG). This procedure can be put under the umbrella of bottom-up synthesis methods, in which pristine graphene is constructed from simple carbon molecules. Among the existing bottom-up techniques, chemical vapor deposition (CVD) growth has exceptional potential to produce endless length multilayer graphene samples. However, bottom-up synthesis methods are proven to be time-consuming and non-scalable, which makes them inconvenient for industrial applications. In this regard, top-down methods, in which layers of graphene derivatives are extracted from a carbon source (typically graphite), have gained attention within researchers. Along this paper, some of the recent advances on the synthesis of chemically modified graphene (CMG) are presented, with particular focus on graphene oxide (GO). Moreover, some considerations and challenges on the utilization of such materials for the manufacturing of microwaves devices are given.

2 Chemically modified graphene

Graphene is a 2D atomically thin layer of sp^2 hybridized carbon atoms organized in a honeycomb structure. Graphite is a 3D stable carbon structure, made of various layers of graphene. When oxidized, graphite can be exfoliated to produce GO [3]. Moreover, GO can be treated to reduce the number of oxygen functional groups and get closer to pristine graphene, resulting in reduced graphene oxide (rGO). The promising properties and synthesis simplicity of GO and rGO has led to many applications such as membranes and coatings, thermal/light/humidity actuators, or batteries. However, their utilization for the fabrication of RF devices has been barely exploited in the literature.

Fig. 1: Schematic of the proposed design strategy for periodic structures including GO.

3 Keys and challenges for microwave applications

The already mentioned properties of graphene, together with its tuneable $50\text{-}\Omega$ impedance, makes it suitable for microwave applications. In fact, graphene has already been used to design various devices including FETs, diodes, absorbers, attenuators or antennas. Among them, many designs exploit the electrically tuneable conductivity of graphene to achieve reconfigurability, which can enable some functionalities such as beam steering or interference mitigation. An exact characterization of the material conductivity is crucial for the design of functional devices. In the case of GO and rGO, this can depend on many factors such as the operating frequency, the oxidation procedure, or the reduction technique. In this regard, it is still a challenge to fully understand the (frequency-dependent) behaviour of GO/rGO conductivity in the microwave range, as well as to determine the most adequate design strategies to exploit material properties optimally. The latter may imply the inclusion of graphene into complex designs to achieve advanced functionalities. Examples of this are metamaterials and 3D metastructures, which provide additional degrees of freedom for the control of the structure behaviour. In this kind of structures, the insertion of GO sheets within the unit cell, together with the possibility of tuning graphene's conductivity by a bias voltage, resulting in two (ON, OFF) states, allows for an electric reconfiguration of the electromagnetic response of the structure. As depicted in Fig. 1, these can be combined with metal elements and various substrates in many possible (3D) unit cell geometries to achieve the desired functionalities of the device.

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